

THE INFLUENCE OF CHRISTIAN LEADERSHIP IN NATION-BUILDING

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INTRODUCTION

Christians who are Christ-like are symbols of purity, love, humility and integrity. Christians, the follower of Jesus Christ are the redeemed of the lord and they are redeemed to live an exemplary live style that can draw, inspire, and influence others who are yet to give their lives to Christ to do so. The followers of Jesus Christ lived and practiced the doctrines and teachings of their master and it was seen in them in Antioch, where there were first called Christians which means Christ-like, as it is recorded in the book of 'Act. 11:26' Jesus led, taught and lived exemplary leadership

style which his followers imbibed, adopted and practiced, and its being passed from one generation to another. Going by this type of leadership set before Christians, Christian leaders have a very vital role in nation building.

One of the major mandates given to Christians is to reach out to the entire world with the message of salvation bringing them to Christ. Saved to save. As Jesus the leader of Christian put it, and he said unto them, “Go ye into the world and preach the gospel to every Creature ‘Mark. 16:15-16’ Go and make disciple of all the nation baptizing them in the name of the father, and of the Son, and of the holy spirit. Teaching them to observed all things whatsoever I have commanded you, and lo, am with you always even unto the end of the world. Mathew 28:19-20. This article intends to highlight the major areas in which Christian leader can contribute to nation building using their position as change and transformation Agents {CTA}. The message of the gospel is about God’s love for man and this gospel can only be preached in love, caring for others and living a moral, honest, decent, disciplinary and exemplary life style that will attract, inspire and draw men unto God.

CHRISTIANS LEADERSHIP INFLUENCE IN NATION BUILDING

Definition Of Terms

Who are these Christians?

Christians are the genuine followers of Jesus Christ, who believe in his birth, death, and resurrection for the salvation of mankind. These are set of people who obey and practice all that Jesus taught and commanded. Christians are the children of almighty God, the children of light who are redeemed, delivered and saved from the power and kingdom of darkness and have been translated into the kingdom of God, the kingdom of light. Christians are set of people that have been called to glory and virtue. They are a chosen generation, a royal priesthood, a peculiar people and holy nation that are called out of darkness into the marvelous light to show forth praises of God and to live according to God’s will. 1 Thessalonians 5:5, 1 Peter 2:9, Colossians’ 1:13, 2 Peter 1:3

What is Christian Leadership?

Christian leadership is that which has its highest aim to glorify God by guiding others to grow in faith and service to God. Leadership Ministry Inc. Aug. 1, 2023

As cited by Olu Mike (2022) say ‘‘Leadership is the action of directing people to do what is right. Leadership means serving others. A leader is like an icon through which other people access their needs’. Christian leadership is modeling behavior and character, building in other good moral by producing in them Godly character and good leadership style through teaching and discipleship.‘1Timothy 4:11-16, 2 Timothy 3:10-15, Philippians 2:4’

Andrew Uncertainty, The Christian Leadership Center said, "Christian Leadership is a dynamic relational process in which people under the influence of the holy spirit, partner to achieve a common goal. It is serving others by leading and leading others by serving'

Christian leadership is a call to serve, to guide and lead others to where they are destined to be or to become in life. It is rendering service unto God and man as will directed by God himself who is the master of all. Christian leadership is not selfish in service, not power hungry nor power tussle but it is being influence by the holy spirit that dwell in their lives, to promote God interest on the earth.

Examples of Contemporary Christian Leadership

Moses at the burning bush was called and assigned with a specific assignment to deliver the children of Israel from the land of slavery, Egypt, and when his tenor ended a successor was pick immediately by God which was Joshua who eventually led the children of Israel to possess the promise land Canaan. Every one have destiny to fulfill, and every nation or people have set of common goal to attain or achieve. All these can only be attain through Godly or good leadership. Whoever comes into leadership position should be able to lead others to fulfillment of their destinies and well ensure that the common goal of the people or nation generally are achieved. Exodus 3:1-10, Joshua 1:1-18, Exodus 17:14, Number 27:18-23, number 17:33.

Further more in example of contemporary Christian Leadership in 21st century is the liberation mandate giving to Bishop David Oyedepo is a practical example of a leader call to lead others into fulfillment of their destiny. As it is stated in the winners mandate ‘ the hour has come to liberate

the world from all oppression of the devil through the preaching of the word of faith and I'm sending you to undertake this task. (Winners mandate). Under this commission the politicians, educators, economists, business men and women as well as leaders in various capacities are being guided rightly in the fulfillment of their destiny.

ATTRIBUTES OF CHRISTIAN LEADERS IN NATION BUILDING

Peace Promoters

According to Merriam Webster Dictionary, peace is; ' a state of tranquility or quietude such as, freedom from civil disturbance. A state of security or order within a community provided for by law or customs. Freedom from disquieting or oppressive thought or emotion. Harmony in personal relations. A state or period of mutual concord between governments'

Christians are peaceful people and they are enjoined to live peacefully with all men Roman 12:18, Matthew 5:9 Christians are peace seekers and peace promoters 1 Timothy 2:2, Psalm 34:14, 1 Peter 3:11

God is a God of peace so all his faithful followers are people of peace, God expects that all people (children) the redeemed live in a peaceable habitation Isa. 32:18. The God of peace has given his children peace as he said 'peace I leave with you, my peace I give unto you not as the world giveth unto you. Let not your heart be troubled, neither be afraid' John 14:27. What can be so vital to nation building than peace. A nation can never be built where there is anarchy, disorder, commotion, crises and lawlessness

Christians are the Light of the World

Matthew 5:14-16 says, ye are the light of the world. A city that is set on a hill cannot be hid. Neither do men light a candle, and put it under a bushel, but on a candlestick, and it giveth light unto all that are in the house. Let your light so shine before men that they may see your father which is in heaven. Light rules over darkness and every evil and wicked activity in the presence of light darkness disappears. Light causes darkness to cease, when there is light no one stumbles or

fumbles. No one is misguided or miscalculate. Things are always done rightly and properly. No one lives in fear, uncertainty frustration or torment. Light prevents evil deed and misconduct. Evil hides and prevail in darkness. Psalm 136:8-9, John 11:9-10, John 3:20-21, John 5:9, Psalm 74:20

Once a Christian move into that department or parastata, the ugly, evil, abominable act that are being condoned tolerated and encouraged will be frown at and atmosphere will change for good. Christians are not to underrate their position when it come to nation building

Love:

God is love and all that must follow him must follow him in love, 1 John 4:8, 1 John 4:16. Christians generally are enjoined to love one another. If anyone should hate his fellow human being then he is a liar, a pretender and the love of God is not in such a person. You cannot claim you love God whom you have not seen when you cannot love the person you see. You will first of all love your fellow human being before you love God whom you have not seen. This will go a long way to build good relationships and make the world a peaceable habitation just as God intends for his people. Love for God is simply to walk in his ordinances and do keep his commandments, which to love man is to treat one with respect and care. John 1:5, 1 John 3:11, 1 John 3:17-18, 1 John 4:7 1 John 4:11, 1 John 4:20-21, 1 John 5:3, 1 John 2:5. Love by deeds and actions not by word or lips. Love for God keep one away from sin while love for man prevents hurting or harming one another. Love is a powerful tool for nation building when you love God with all your heart, with all your strength, with all your soul and with all your mind, and then loving your neighbor just as you love yourself as it written in the book of Mathew 22:37-38, Mark 12:30-33, Luke 10:27, so life is about love and care. The Golden Rule- Treating one as you would want them to treat you. No one will want or intend to hurt or harm himself. No one want to be treated badly or cruelly. No one would want to be betrayed, molested, abused, rubbed, offended. No one would want to be rough handled. Living by this rule helps build a better society and a better nation as everyone will behave well and normal. Christians who know better will not only teach but live an exemplary life style that will influence the society. Mathew 7:12. Treat others the way you would want to be treated. Our society will be a better place to dwell.

Virtues:

Christians are called to glory and virtue. 1 Peter 1:3. They are admonished to live a virtues life. The rules also said in the book of Proverbs 12:4 that a virtues woman is a crown to her husband. Virtuosi which is a moral excellence, a good quality that promote decency, serenity and peaceful coexistence. Philippians.4:8 says; ‘finally brethren, whatsoever things are true, whatsoever things that are honest, whatsoever things that are just, whatsoever things that are pure, whatsoever things are lovely and whatsoever are good. Report, if there be any virtue and if there be any praise, think on these things.’ Christian’s minds are not to be polluted with evil thought and imaginations that will cause harm, endanger or put the society in jeopardy. Actions are products of thoughts from the mind. The mind is the bakery where evil emanate from. Things don’t just happened, there are cooked, fabricated, processed in the mind, them brings forth into manifestation. Jesus speaking in the book of Mark 7:15-25 and Mathew 15:18-20 says that what really defiles and corrupt a man is what comes from the heart not what he eats. Also, in the book of Proverb 4:23 says “keep thy heart with all diligence for out of it are the issue of life. Thinking have the capacity to ruin or to build, has the ability to mar or make a nation

Contentment

1 Timothy 6:6 ‘But godliness with contentment is great gain’ living right and being satisfy with whatsoever one has or the level attained in life is one of the features of Christians. Not being greedy or desperate. As fraud, embezzlement, get rich quick, unhealthy rivalry, power turtle has become the order of the day in our society. Christians leadership influence in nation building must not convert public funds into private use but should be used judiciously. Don’t kill because of position or affluence. Proverb 28:20 says ‘a faithful man shall abound with blessings’ but he that maketh haste to be rich shall not be innocent’ Blessings are not about hard work but getting favour to live above suffering, hardship, lack and difficulties in life. To be blessed is to live a comfortable satisfied joyful and peaceful life. Godliness and contentment is great gain.

Humility

Humility is another attribute of Christian leadership influence in nation building. Humility which is the state or quality of being humble. Also, a life without pride or arrogance. The bible says in the book of proverb 15;33 that before honor is humility. If anyone want to be honor in life, he has

to be first of all be humble. Also speaking in the book of Titus 3:2 that Christians should not speak evil of any one, nor be brawlers, but to be gentle and to showing all meekness to everyone. With this virtues in the lives of Christians, the society indeed will be a serene place. Christians are to live and behave respectfully at any giving time irrespective of what happened around them. Christians teach these things and also to live by them. 'By humility and the fear of the lord are riches and honor and life' according Proverb 22;4. Riches are not through stealing, embezzlement, fraud but by living right.

CHRISTIAN LEADERSHIP IN NATION BUILDING

Christian leadership is a kind of leadership that is influenced, led, motivated and guided by the help of the holy spirit. It is a kind of leadership that is being patterned after Jesus Christ who taught, lived and laid down good example of good and effective leadership. A Christian leader who is filled with the holy spirit, who humbled himself under the influence, dictate and guidance of the holy spirit. A Christian leader operates with divine wisdom that come from above {the father} which is Godly, pure and perfect in discharging his duties. A Christian leader submits to the higher authority, and obey all the rules and regulations and also lives and practices all the biblical principle. A Christian leader is being taught by the holy spirit. Roman 8:14, James 3:15-17, John 14:26, Roman 13:1. Christian leadership influence in nation building can never be an overstatement as they are the ambassadors of God and they represent God's interest on the earth. God's intention for his children is to turn and convert the lost souls into his kingdom. The primary assignment of every Christian is soul winning and converting, by influencing the world positively not just by teaching and preaching but by good lifestyle.

Nation Building

According to Marriam Webster Dictionary nation building is 'to build is to put things together to become one whole. To build is to form by ordering and unifying materials by gradual means into a complete whole. To develop according to a systematic plan by a definite process or on a particular base'

Nation building is a process, an act in which human, financial and materials resources are put together to enhance a common goal of a people. Ingredients, materials and resources required for nation building are, personal traits, potential, skills, talent and gifting. Nation building is a process in which people in a given community contribute meaningfully for the peace, harmony, development that will form a unified and peaceful serenity.

Before a nation could talk about nation building, the nation has to first of all consider building her citizens. It is when her citizens are properly built and equipped that effective nation building can be adequately achieved, what can a sick and decayed citizens possibly build. It is people who serve or work in the political, educational and economic sector of every society. It takes sound minded and healthy people, competent and discipline citizens to build a sound and healthy society that is void of corruption crises, lawlessness, tribalism, terrorism, banditry, sentiment, threat to life, cultism, killing, rioting, kidnapping. Nation building or development is completely in the hands of sound minded individuals who are well trained, properly equipped and are skills full that will effectively pilot the affairs of any nation. Nation building is a collective and collaborated effort and systematic procession from one state or level to another.

RECOMMENDATION

If Christian must influence the world positively, they must be ready to make all the necessary sacrifices to ensure that is achieved. Christians leaders are to use their positions to transform our society into a better place. Christian leaders are to show that they are the light set to remove evil and wickedness in the world. Christian leaders should use Bible as a tool for effective leadership and for the transformation of the society.

CONCLUSION

Christians leadership influence In nation building is crucial as Christian leaders are the change agent that the word have been waiting for. Romans 8;19-22 says, 'for the earnest expectation of the creature waited for the manifestation of the sons of God. The creature was made subject to vanity, not willingly but by reason of him who had subjected the same in hope because the creature

itself also shall be delivered from the bondage of corruption into the glorious liberty of the children of God, for we know that the whole creation groaneth and travelled in pain together until now' Christians are the change Agents that the world has been waiting for. Our society is decaying, corruption has eaten deep into the fabrics of the society. The children of God have to manifest their gifts virtue love and care. The groaning, travelling in pain, bondage and social decadence is really alarming and terrible and call for urgent attention.

The earnest expectation of the creature waiting all this while to see the children of God in action to be delivered from the horrible bondage of corruption into its glorious liberty of the children of God. The mandate has always been, go ye into the world and make disciple of all Nations teaching them to observe all. Baptizing them, that is to get them inducted or initiated into the family of the saints, the family of light. Where are the ambassadors of heaven, where are the lights of the world, where are the Christ-like? Children of God, the time to manifest is now! The time to deliver the world from the bondage of corruption is now!

About The Author

Apostle (Prof.) Ushie Francis Inde hails from Obudu in Cross River State, Nigeria. He is a Christian Educator and Church Administrator. Apostle Ushie is also a Trainer and Counselor with Passion for Soul Winning and Reconciliation. Apostle Ushie started his ministry service with Mount Zion Missions as an Evangelist at the age of 17, where he engaged in rugged evangelism and grew in that might. He further extended his ministerial services with Living Spring Assembly and City Harvest Ministry, all in Jos, the Plateau State Capital, before starting Straightway Divine Christian Outreach. Inc., in the city of Abuja in March 2015. Apostle Ushie Francis is the Registrar General of the Institute of Christian Theologians, Scholars, and Professionals. He is also a Rector at Freedom University and Theological Seminary on one of her campuses in the city of Abuja. Where he obtained his BA, MA, and PhD, and thereafter, Professorship Laureate. He is happily married and blessed with wonderful children. Correspondence: straightwaydivine@gmail.com. +2348036599807.

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